

School Management Factors Influencing Teachers' Job Satisfaction. (A Study based on Teachers of the Beruwala Division Schools)

F.A.F, Fazna
Faculty of Education, University of Colombo

Dr.V.Vijayabaskar
Department of Education, Faculty of Arts, University
of Jaffna

Abstract

Teacher job satisfaction plays a crucial role in ensuring educational quality, institutional effectiveness and student achievement. While previous studies have examined determinants of teacher satisfaction at national and district levels, limited research has focused on school-level management factors within minority-language educational contexts in Sri Lanka. This study investigates the level of teacher job satisfaction in Tamil medium government schools in the Beruwala Education Division and examines the influence of human resource and physical resource management factors. A sequential explanatory mixed-methods design was employed. Quantitative data were collected from 94 teachers across eight schools using a structured questionnaire (Cronbach's $\alpha=.78$). Descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analyses were conducted using PSPP software. To enrich the quantitative findings, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 16 teachers and analyzed thematically. Findings indicated that overall teacher job satisfaction was moderately high ($M=3.69$). One-way ANOVA revealed significant differences among schools ($p=.016$). A moderate positive relationship was observed between school management factors and job satisfaction ($r=.592, p<.001$). The regression model explained 40% of the variance in job satisfaction (Adjusted $R^2=.40$), with administrative support identified as the strongest predictor ($\beta=.40, p<.001$). Qualitative results highlighted participatory leadership, transparent communication, equitable delegation and adequate facilities as key contributors to teacher satisfaction. Effective administrative support and sound school

management practices significantly enhance teacher job satisfaction. Strengthening leadership responsiveness and improving resource management systems may contribute to teacher well-being and educational quality in minority-language school settings.

Keywords:

teacher job satisfaction; school management; administrative support; leadership; human resource management; physical resource management

School Management Factors Influencing Teacher Job Satisfaction in Tamil Medium Schools of the Beruwala Division

This research article is structured under the following sections:

1. Introduction
2. Literature Review
3. Research Methodology
4. Data Analysis, Discussion, Conclusions and Recommendations

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Teachers are key determinants of educational quality and school development. Their level of job satisfaction significantly influences their performance, instructional effectiveness, professional commitment and overall engagement in school activities. Furthermore, teacher job satisfaction has a direct impact on students' academic achievement. Within the Sri Lankan context, several studies have identified factors such as salary structures, professional development opportunities, interpersonal relationships and working conditions as influential determinants of teacher job satisfaction (Priyadarshini, 2024; Karunarathne, 2020; Ratnayake & Jagoda,

2023).

Additionally, Principals' leadership styles, administrative support, conflict management practices, and workload have been shown to significantly influence teacher job satisfaction (Bogler, 2001; Collie et al., 2012; Leithwood & Jantzi, 2005; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011). However, there is limited clarity regarding the specific school management factors that contribute to variations in job satisfaction

1.2 Research Problem and Gap

In Tamil medium schools of the Beruwala Division, variations in teacher job satisfaction levels are observed even within the same school. Teachers with high job satisfaction tend to assume greater responsibilities and actively contribute to school development. In contrast, teachers with lower job satisfaction are more likely to take frequent leave, demonstrate limited engagement in school activities and experience conflicts with administration. Such disparities present challenges to school management and negatively affect students' educational processes.

Research Gap

Due to the unique socio-cultural characteristics of the Beruwala region, findings from previous studies cannot be fully generalized to this context. This highlights the necessity for context-specific research. Accordingly, this study was undertaken to identify the school management factors contributing to variations in teacher job satisfaction within the Beruwala Division and to explain their implications for teacher satisfaction and overall school development.

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

Research Aim

To identify the key factors influencing teacher job satisfaction in Tamil medium schools of the Beruwala Division.

Research Objectives

1. To assess the level of job satisfaction among teachers working in Tamil medium schools of the Beruwala Division.
2. To identify human resource management factors within schools that influence teacher job satisfaction.
3. To identify physical resource management

among teachers within Tamil medium government schools in the Beruwala Division. Even within the same school, noticeable differences in job satisfaction levels exist among teachers. Therefore, this study examines the level of teacher job satisfaction in the Beruwala Division and identifies the school management factors shaping it and proposes recommendations for improvement.

factors within schools that influence teacher job satisfaction.

1.4 Contribution of the Study

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing context-specific empirical evidence on school management factors influencing teacher job satisfaction within Tamil medium government schools in the Beruwala Division of Sri Lanka. While previous studies have examined teacher job satisfaction at National and District levels, limited attention has been given to minority-language educational contexts characterized by distinct socio-cultural and administrative conditions. By integrating quantitative and qualitative evidence, this study offers a nuanced understanding of how leadership practices and administrative support mechanisms operate at the school level. The findings provide practical implications for school leaders, policymakers and educational administrators seeking to enhance teacher well-being and institutional effectiveness in similar socio-cultural settings.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This section reviews previous studies and theoretical foundations related to school management factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction. It provides a conceptual and empirical basis for understanding how management practices within schools affect teachers' professional well-being and performance.

2.2 Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is primarily guided by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959) and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory which provide foundational

explanations of job satisfaction and human motivation.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959)

According to Herzberg, job satisfaction and dissatisfaction arise from two distinct categories of factors: motivators and hygiene factors.

Hygiene factors (ex. salary, working conditions, institutional policies and administrative practices) do not directly create job satisfaction; however, their absence or inadequacy leads to dissatisfaction. These factors are essential for preventing negative attitudes but are insufficient to generate sustained motivation. In contrast, motivators (ex. recognition, professional growth, achievement, responsibility and advancement) contribute directly to enhanced job satisfaction and intrinsic motivation.

In the context of Tamil medium schools in the Beruwala Division, aspects such as school leadership, organizational climate and administrative procedures function as hygiene factors while opportunities for professional development, participation in decision-making and recognition serve as motivators. Herzberg's theory thus provides a framework for analyzing how school management practices may either reduce dissatisfaction or actively enhance teacher job satisfaction.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow's theory proposes that individuals strive to satisfy a hierarchy of five levels of needs: physiological, safety, social, esteem and self-actualization. According to this model, higher levels of satisfaction cannot be achieved unless lower-level needs are adequately fulfilled.

Within the school context, teachers' physiological needs are addressed through salary, safety needs through job security; social needs through collegial and principal-teacher relationships; esteem needs through recognition and appreciation; and self-actualization needs through opportunities for professional growth and career advancement. These theoretical perspectives collectively expand the understanding of teacher job satisfaction beyond financial considerations, emphasizing its multidimensional nature and its connection to broader aspects of human well-being.

2.3 Empirical Review

Job satisfaction is commonly defined as the positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences and professional achievements.

A review of studies conducted in Sri Lanka indicates that teachers generally report moderate to relatively high levels of job satisfaction. Ratnayake and Jagoda (2023), in their study of government school teachers in the Nuwara Eliya District, found that female teachers demonstrated a higher probability of job satisfaction compared to male teachers. Many studies have reported that a majority of teachers expressed high levels of job satisfaction.

However, some studies reveal that even when teachers report satisfaction, there remains a significant intention to leave the profession, suggesting that satisfaction alone may not guarantee retention. Regional studies in Sri Lanka further highlight variations in teacher job satisfaction levels across different contexts. These differences are often associated with variations in school climate and management practices.

Overall, empirical evidence suggests that school environment and management-related factors play a decisive role in shaping teachers' job satisfaction, reinforcing the need for context-specific investigations such as the present study.

2.3.1.School Management Factors Influencing Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Educational management is the systematic planning, organizing, directing and controlling of human and material resources to achieve educational objectives (Hoy, W. K. , & Miskel, C. G. 2013).

It encompasses both human and physical resource management processes aimed at ensuring the delivery of quality education (Ministry of Education, 2014).

In this regard, school management factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction are categorized under two major domains:

- 1.Human Resource Management factors
- 2.Physical Resource Management factors

These domains are reviewed below with reference to relevant empirical evidence

2.3.2.Human Resource Management Factors Influencing Teachers' Job

Satisfaction

Teacher management within schools is grounded in human resource policies regulated by national education policies and guidelines. School principals and administrative leadership play a central role in creating a positive working environment that fosters teacher job satisfaction.

Human resource management contributes significantly to enhancing organizational effectiveness, employee retention, job satisfaction, commitment and professional integrity (Edgar & Greare, 2005; Rahman, 2013). It also facilitates alignment between individual, professional, organizational and social goals (Jeyarasa, 2017).

Key human resource management practices include fair recruitment, promotion, transfer procedures, performance-based rewards, transparent administrative processes, responsiveness to employee concerns, resilience in crisis situations, social responsibility and effective communication (Jeyarasa, 2017).

Among HRM factors, leadership style is widely recognized as a critical determinant of teacher job satisfaction. Bogler (2001) found that democratic leadership increases teacher job satisfaction, whereas autocratic leadership contributes to dissatisfaction. Leithwood and Jantzi (2006) argue that transformational leadership positively motivates teachers. Similarly, Hoy and Miskel (2013) emphasize that participative leadership enhances teachers' positive attitudes toward their profession. Leadership that adapts appropriately to situational demands tends to produce positive outcomes, whereas rigid and inappropriate leadership approaches may negatively affect satisfaction.

Decision-making processes and conflict management practices also significantly influence teachers' job satisfaction. Effective conflict resolution within schools contributes positively to teacher morale and work environment quality. Effective leadership practices, including constructive conflict management and supportive administrative behavior, positively influence teachers' job satisfaction (Bogler, 2001; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011).

Furthermore, delegation of authority, clarity of roles and responsibilities, working conditions, and administrative support are crucial determinants. Challenges related to

career progression and promotion procedures within the education sector often affect teacher morale. Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2011) found that administrative support reduces teacher stress and prevents attrition. Trust-based relationships between teachers and school leaders foster a positive organizational climate and enhance job satisfaction.

Although previous studies have examined human resource management practices and their impact on teacher job satisfaction, findings are sometimes inconsistent and limited by cultural and contextual variations. Particularly within the Sri Lankan context and more specifically in the Beruwala Division, there is a noticeable gap in localized empirical research addressing these factors comprehensively. This gap justifies the present study.

2.3.3. Physical Resource Management Factors Influencing Teachers' Job Satisfaction

The physical environment includes all non-living elements such as land, water, air, infrastructure and climatic conditions that influence human activity (UNEP, 2020). In educational settings the physical working environment plays a significant role in shaping teachers' confidence, motivation and overall job satisfaction.

In many schools, adequate facilities for teachers remain insufficient. Basic amenities such as staff rooms, parking facilities, sanitation facilities, canteens and access to safe drinking water are not consistently available. Teachers working in rural and under-resourced urban schools frequently encounter such infrastructural challenges (Sinayathamby, 2004).

These inadequacies not only create daily professional difficulties but also affect teachers' economic stability and family life, especially where opportunities for supplementary income are limited. Despite these challenges, limited attention is given to providing appropriate incentives, career advancement opportunities, higher education pathways or welfare support for teachers serving in disadvantaged contexts.

To mitigate teacher dissatisfaction, collaborative efforts involving school administration, parents, educational authorities and transport service providers are necessary to ensure affordable and reliable

transportation. Additionally, provision of accommodation facilities, healthy midday meal arrangements and improved workplace amenities could significantly reduce teacher frustration and enhance professional engagement (Sinayathamby, 2004).

2.3.4. Dimensions for Measuring Teacher Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a multidimensional psychological construct. Therefore, accurately assessing teachers' job satisfaction requires identifying its key dimensions. In this regard the Job Satisfaction Scale developed by T. S. Nanjundeswaraswamy (2019) is considered a reliable and widely applicable measurement instrument. Through factor analysis, eight core dimensions of job satisfaction were identified:

1. Salary and welfare benefits
2. Working environment (physical conditions, safety, facilities, technology and resources)
3. Leadership practices (guidance, fairness, support, motivation, recognition)
4. Communication, workload, and role clarity
5. Work-life balance
6. Training and professional development opportunities
7. Career advancement and promotion opportunities
8. Job security and teamwork

These dimensions provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating teacher job satisfaction in a structured and context-sensitive manner.

2.3.5. Consequences of Varying Levels of Teacher Job Satisfaction

International research consistently indicates that higher levels of teacher job satisfaction contribute positively to student academic achievement. A strong, positive and statistically significant relationship has been observed between teacher job satisfaction and instructional effectiveness as well as overall school performance. Conversely low levels of job satisfaction are often associated with burnout stress and reduced professional engagement. Several studies conducted in Sri Lanka further confirm these findings. Empirical evidence indicates that higher teacher job satisfaction is positively associated with instructional effectiveness and student academic achievement (Caprara et al., 2006; Klassen & Chiu, 2010). Similarly, Ratnayake

and Jagoda (2023), in their study of government schools in the Nuwara Eliya District, emphasized that teacher job satisfaction is a fundamental prerequisite for improved school effectiveness.

Conversely, numerous studies indicate that low job satisfaction increases teachers' intention to leave the profession. In the context of Sri Lanka's current economic challenges, teachers' mental well-being has been adversely affected, intensifying dissatisfaction and occupational stress. When teachers experience dissatisfaction within the school environment, absenteeism and reduced participation in school activities tend to increase. In contrast, higher levels of job satisfaction are associated with stronger organizational commitment, increased morale and greater professional dedication.

Thus, teacher job satisfaction has far-reaching implications not only for individual well-being but also for institutional stability and student achievement.

2.3.6. Recommendations for Enhancing Teacher Job Satisfaction

Both international and Sri Lankan studies highlight that effective management strategies significantly enhance teacher job satisfaction. School principals are encouraged to adopt distributed leadership practices by empowering subject heads, sectional leaders and teacher leaders. Leadership practices should also be integrated into measurable school development plans. Research indicates that teachers' job satisfaction increases when they meaningfully participate in school-level decision-making processes, including planning, timetable preparation and curriculum modifications. However such participation must be genuine and followed by concrete administrative actions to be effective (Priyadarshani, 2024). Transparent promotion criteria and clear salary structures contribute to long-term teacher retention and improved morale (Diagne, 2023; Priyadarshani, 2024). Priority should be given to professional development programs that directly support classroom practices. Establishing merit-based career advancement pathways linked to demonstrable competencies can further enhance professional motivation.

Excessive administrative tasks, unfair timetabling and non-teaching duties are identified as major contributors to job dissatisfaction and burnout. Workload reduction initiatives have been shown to decrease absenteeism and improve teacher well-being (OECD; Ranathunga, 2022).

While salary increases alone produce mixed results, non-monetary recognition—such as awards, public appreciation and professional incentives—consistently strengthens morale, particularly when evaluation criteria are fair, transparent and clearly communicated (Priyadarshani, 2024).

Based on the reviewed literature, enhancing teacher job satisfaction requires improvements in principal leadership style, transparency in decision-making fairness in promotions and incentives meaningful recognition mechanisms and structured opportunities for professional growth.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the methodological framework adopted to examine teachers' job satisfaction levels and the school management factors influencing them. It outlines the research design, study area, population, sampling procedures and data collection instruments employed in the study.

3.2. Study Area

This study was conducted in the Beruwala Division, which falls under the Kalutara Education Zone in the Kalutara District of the Western Province of Sri Lanka. The Beruwala region is characterized by historical, linguistic, social and economic diversity. It consists of heterogeneous community groups with varied socio-cultural backgrounds, making it a contextually significant setting for examining teacher job satisfaction within Tamil medium government schools.

3.3. Research Approach

This study adopted a mixed-method approach, integrating quantitative data to measure the extent of teacher job satisfaction with qualitative data to capture experiences, perceptions and contextual explanations. The integration of both approaches enables a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

3.3.1. Research Design

The study employed a Sequential Explanatory Mixed-Methods Design.

In the first phase, quantitative data were collected and analyzed to identify patterns and trends in teacher job satisfaction levels. In the second phase, qualitative data were gathered to explain and interpret the underlying reasons behind the observed quantitative results.

3.3.2. Sequential Explanatory Procedure

The research process began with the collection of quantitative data using structured questionnaires. Teachers' job satisfaction levels were measured and analyzed to identify key trends within the Beruwala Division. Based on the quantitative findings, selected teachers were invited to participate in semi-structured interviews. These interviews aimed to provide deeper insights into the factors contributing to the identified satisfaction patterns.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings ensured triangulation, thereby enhancing the reliability and credibility of the study.

3.4. Population and Sampling

The target population of this study comprised all teachers working in Tamil medium government schools in the Beruwala Division. This population is heterogeneous, varying in terms of gender, years of experience, subject specialization, service category and administrative responsibilities.

3.4.1. Sampling Method

A stratified sampling method was employed in this study. Since teachers in the Beruwala Division differ across multiple characteristics, such as gender, experience, subject area and educational level. Stratified sampling was selected to ensure adequate representation of each subgroup. Considering the scope and time constraints of the study 20% of teachers from each stratum were selected as the sample.

3.5. Data Collection Instruments

Data were collected using two primary instruments:

1. Structured questionnaire
2. Semi-structured interviews

Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale was developed to measure teachers' job satisfaction levels quantitatively.

The questionnaire consisted of two sections:

1. Demographic Information

- Gender
- Age
- Years of service
- Position
- Subject specialization

2. Job Satisfaction Variables

- Working environment
- Administrative support
- Principal–teacher relationship
- Leadership practices
- Resource availability and allocation

Interviews

To explain trends emerging from the quantitative data> semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with selected teachers. Each interview lasted approximately 30–45 minutes. Responses were recorded using audio recordings and note-taking methods.

The qualitative data provided contextual explanations for the statistical findings obtained in the first phase

4. Data Analysis and Findings

Quantitative data obtained through questionnaires were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive analysis included percentages, means and standard deviations. Inferential analysis employed Independent Sample Tests, One-Way ANOVA, Correlation Analysis and Multiple Regression to examine relationships, differences and predictive effects between job satisfaction and school management factors. All quantitative analyses were conducted using SPSS software.

Qualitative data collected through interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis (coding → categorization → theme development).

4.1. Results of Quantitative Data Analysis

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics

1. Reliability Analysis

The reliability of the overall job satisfaction scale was tested using Cronbach's Alpha. The obtained value was $\alpha = 0.78$, indicating

acceptable internal consistency. This confirms that the questionnaire instrument was reliable and suitable for the study.

2. Mean and Standard Deviation

The overall mean job satisfaction score of 94 teachers was: $M = 3.69$ ($n = 94$). When analyzed by school, the highest mean score was recorded in School 04 ($M = 3.88$), while the lowest was observed in School 02 ($M = 3.41$). These findings indicate that teacher job satisfaction in the study context can be described as moderately high.

4.1.2. Inferential Statistics

1. One-Way ANOVA

Before conducting ANOVA, the assumption of homogeneity of variances was tested using Levene's Test, which was non-significant ($p = 0.324$), indicating that the assumption was satisfied. The results of the One-Way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference in teacher job satisfaction across schools: $F(7, 86) = 2.64$, $p = 0.016$

Since $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis ("There is no difference in job satisfaction among schools") was rejected. This confirms that teacher job satisfaction significantly varies across schools within the Beruwala Division, likely due to differences in school management and contextual factors.

Post-hoc analysis (Tukey test) indicated a significant mean difference between School 04 and School 02: Mean Difference = 0.47, $p = 0.018$.

This suggests that teachers in School 04 experience significantly higher job satisfaction than those in School 02.

2. Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between school management factors and teacher job satisfaction. The results indicated a moderate to strong positive correlation: $r = 0.592$, $p < 0.001$

This suggests that improvements in management factors—such as leadership practices, administrative support, interpersonal relationships, resource availability, and equitable resource allocation—are associated with higher levels of teacher job satisfaction.

3. Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was performed to identify key management predictors of teacher job satisfaction. The regression model was statistically significant: $F(7, 70) = 3.69$. $p < 0.001$

Model statistics:

- $R = 0.74$

- $R^2 = 0.55$

- Adjusted $R^2 = 0.40$

Based on the Adjusted R^2 value, approximately 40% of the variance in teacher job satisfaction is explained collectively by the selected management factors. Among the predictors, administrative support emerged as the strongest individual predictor: $\beta \approx 0.40$, $p < 0.001$. This indicates that administrative support plays a central role in determining teachers' job satisfaction levels.

4.1.3. Qualitative Data Analysis

To explain the quantitative findings, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 16 teachers from 8 schools. Thematic analysis identified the following key themes:

- Leadership style
- Principal–teacher relationship
- Administrative support
- Delegation of authority and responsibility
- Physical working environment
- Resource allocation practices

Teachers reported that participative leadership, transparent communication, timely administrative support, and fair decision-making processes enhanced job satisfaction.

Conversely, dissatisfaction was associated with unilateral decision-making, poor communication, delays in decision implementation, lack of transparency, favoritism, resource shortages and inequitable resource distribution.

4.1.4. Integrated Quantitative–Qualitative Interpretation

Both quantitative and qualitative findings converged to provide consistent evidence. Quantitative analysis demonstrated:

- A significant positive relationship between management factors and job satisfaction ($r = 0.592$).
- Significant differences in job satisfaction across schools ($p = 0.016$).
- Administrative support as a key predictor (β

≈ 0.40).

Qualitative findings further explained the institutional mechanisms underlying these statistical relationships. Teachers consistently identified administrative support as the central factor shaping their daily professional experiences and overall job satisfaction.

Thus, the integrated findings confirm that school-level management practices. Particularly administrative support and leadership style play a decisive role in influencing teacher job satisfaction in the Beruwala Division.

5. Discussion

This study examined the level of teacher job satisfaction in Tamil medium government schools in the Beruwala Division and identified key school management factors influencing it. The findings indicate that overall teacher job satisfaction is moderately high ($M = 3.69$), yet significant differences exist across schools. These variations suggest that job satisfaction is shaped not merely by individual characteristics but by school-level management practices and contextual factors.

The significant difference in job satisfaction across schools ($F(7, 86) = 2.64$, $p = 0.016$) supports the assumption that institutional practices and leadership approaches influence teachers' professional experiences. Schools demonstrating higher satisfaction levels appear to maintain more supportive administrative systems and participatory leadership practices. This finding aligns with prior research emphasizing the importance of school climate and leadership in shaping teacher morale (Bogler, 2001; Collie et al., 2012).

The positive correlation between school management factors and job satisfaction ($r = 0.592$, $p < 0.001$) indicates a moderately strong relationship. This suggests that improvements in leadership practices > administrative support, communication and resource allocation are likely to enhance teacher job satisfaction. These findings are consistent with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, where administrative policies and working conditions function as hygiene factors that prevent dissatisfaction, while recognition and participation serve as motivators enhancing satisfaction.

The regression analysis further revealed that approximately 40% of the variance in teacher job satisfaction is explained by the selected management factors (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.40$). Among these, administrative support emerged as the strongest predictor ($\beta \approx 0.40$, $p < 0.001$). This highlights the central role of supportive leadership in fostering teacher well-being. Teachers who perceive timely assistance, fairness in decision-making and open communication from school leadership are more likely to report higher levels of satisfaction.

The qualitative findings reinforce and deepen the quantitative results. Teachers emphasized that participative leadership, transparent communication, fair delegation of responsibilities and equitable resource distribution significantly enhance job satisfaction. Conversely, unilateral decision-making, favoritism and inadequate resource allocation were associated with dissatisfaction. The convergence of quantitative and qualitative findings strengthens the credibility of the study and confirms that administrative support and leadership style are decisive factors influencing teacher job satisfaction in this context.

These findings also align with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Administrative support contributes to teachers' sense of safety and belonging, while recognition and participation in decision-making address esteem and self-actualization needs. Therefore, teacher job satisfaction should be understood as a multidimensional construct influenced by both structural and relational aspects of school management.

Overall, this study confirms that school-level management practices play a critical role in shaping teachers' professional satisfaction within minority-language educational settings. While national policies provide structural frameworks, the day-to-day experiences of teachers are largely determined by school leadership and internal management systems.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

This study investigated school management factors influencing teacher job satisfaction in Tamil medium government schools in the Beruwala Division. The findings reveal that teacher job satisfaction in the study area is

moderately high but varies significantly across schools. These variations are strongly associated with differences in leadership practices, administrative support and resource management.

The results demonstrate a significant positive relationship between school management factors and teacher job satisfaction. Administrative support was identified as the most influential predictor. The study therefore concludes that effective school-level management, particularly supportive and participative leadership, plays a decisive role in enhancing teacher satisfaction, professional commitment and overall school effectiveness. By integrating quantitative and qualitative evidence, this research provides context-specific insights into how management practices influence teacher well-being in minority-language schools. The findings emphasize that improving teacher job satisfaction requires not only policy-level reforms but also strengthened school-based leadership practices.

6.2. Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthening Administrative Support

School principals should establish structured support systems to address teachers' professional and personal concerns promptly. Open communication channels and responsive administrative practices should be institutionalized.

2. Promoting Participative Leadership

Principals are encouraged to adopt participative and distributed leadership approaches by involving teachers in decision-making processes related to timetabling, curriculum planning and school development initiatives.

3. Ensuring Transparency and Fairness

Transparent procedures in delegation of responsibilities, performance evaluation and recognition mechanisms should be implemented to reduce perceptions of favoritism and enhance trust.

4. Improving Resource Allocation

Equitable distribution of physical and instructional resources should be prioritized. Schools with limited facilities should receive targeted support from zonal and provincial education authorities.

5. Professional Development Opportunities

Continuous professional development programs aligned with classroom needs should be provided to enhance teachers' competence, motivation and career advancement prospects.

6. Policy-Level Support

Educational authorities should integrate leadership training and administrative competency development into principal appointment and promotion frameworks to ensure effective school-level management.

6.3. Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

This study was limited to Tamil medium government schools within the Beruwala Division and therefore may not be generalizable to other regions or language streams. Additionally, the sample size and the number of predictors in regression analysis may limit the explanatory power of the model. Future research could:

- Expand the study to multiple districts
- Conduct longitudinal investigations
- Compare Sinhala and Tamil medium schools
- Explore the mediating role of organizational culture.

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